

The soil coring method: Measuring root traits down the soil profile in field conditions

Problem

Root systems and their interactions with the soil are crucial for crop performance, through the capture of water and nutrients. These root functions are important for improving resource use efficiency and enhancing crop resilience against climate change. There can be many limitations to crop rooting, such as nutrition, over or under supply of water, soil compaction and structure or agronomic management.

Solution

To evaluate how effectively a crop has established its root system in a specific environment, and to assess potential differences between varieties or the impact of treatments such as cultivation methods or agrochemicals, it is necessary to collect soil samples at depth to measure root development throughout the soil profile. The soil coring method was developed to measure root length density (RLD), diameter and root biomass at different soil depths, in field conditions. The method presented here is based on the ADAS standard operating procedure, shared during the Root2Res project.

Principle

The soil coring method involves collecting a soil core down to a metre depth, either mechanically or by hand. The roots are then washed from the soil at different depths and analysed for various traits, using software such as WinRhizo or RhizoVision. After analysis, the sampled roots are oven dried, and biomass is measured. For crops sown in rows it's recommended to take an equal number of cores within and between the rows.

Benefits and weaknesses

Soil coring enables the assessment of root length, diameter and biomass to depth, commonly between 0 and 100 cm depth, although deeper samples can be collected if a longer auger is used. This method is applicable to a wide range of crops. However, it is a time and labour intensive method and therefore not suitable when analysing large trials or breeding programmes.

Applicability box

Theme: Root measurements

Relevance: Soil coring enables measuring root traits down the soil profile between 0 and 100 cm depth (deeper if equipment allows)

Best in: combinable crops; between flowering and immediately after harvest when the root system has reached its maximum size

Measured traits within a plot/field area:

- Root biomass (g/cm³ of soil)
- Root length density (cm/cm³ of soil)
- Average root diameter (mm)
- Length of root in different diameter classes (cm or % of total root length in diameter class)

Required time: 6 cores per plot

Sampling: 1h/plot

Washing and scanning: 5h/plot

Practical recommendations

In each plot, take six 30 mm diameter soil cores to a depth of 100 cm using a window sampler/auger (Figure 1). The number, length and diameter of the samples taken can be adjusted based on available resources or specific requirements. The depth and diameter of each sample should be recorded to calculate the volume of soil in the sample. Typically 1 meter samples (Figure 2) are divided into 5 horizons of 20 cm each. It is recommended to use a mechanical machine such as a hydraulic hammer/auger to collect the soil cores and to freeze the samples until they are analysed.

For root analysis, wash the roots carefully from the soil with water (Figure 3) and pick out any non-root matter from the sample (Figure 4). To analyse the roots for different traits, spread the sample in a shallow tray of water and capture an image using a flat-bed scanner (Figure 5). This image can then be analysed using software, such as WinRhizo to measure root length, surface area and diameter. After scan-

ning, oven dry the samples and record the dry weight. Root measurements should be done within 24 hours of washing to avoid sample degradation.

The depth and diameter of the soil core determine the soil volume, which is used to calculate root traits, such as root length density (cm of root in a cm^3 of soil), and root biomass (g/cm^3) at different soil depths.

Figure 1: Hydraulic soil corer.

Figure 2: Soil core.

Figure 3: Root washing apparatus.

Figure 4: Picking out non-root matter from the sample.

Figure 5: Tray of water with sample on a flatbed scanner.

Further information

- Clarke, C. K., et al. (2017). Quantifying rooting at depth in a wheat doubled haploid populations with introgression from wild emmer. *Annals of Botany*; doi [10.1093/aob/mcx068](https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcx068).
- White, C. A., et al. (2015). Root length densities of UK wheat and oilseed rape crops with implications for water capture and yield. *Journal of Experimental Botany*; doi [10.1093/jxb/erv077](https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erv077).
- For WinRhizo see : <https://regent.qc.ca/assets/references.html#winhizo>
- Video Soil coring: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e7qtD4fiRoA&list=PLHg-KjCtaNtTwXRFzhLMLbOsYyRjY9uhZ&index=6>
- Video Root washing: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kR7kGjkdjE&list=PLHg-KjCtaNtTwXRFzhLMLbOsYyRjY9uhZ&index=3>

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

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Project website: root2res.eu

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